

Efficacy of biorational insecticides against major sucking pests of okra

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ABSTRACT: Investigations were carried out on the effect of biorational insecticides against sucking pests of okra during 2015-16 at the ICAR-Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bengaluru. The major sucking insects studied were leafhopper, *Amrasca biguttula biguttula* Ishida, whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* Gennadius, and aphid, *Aphis gossypii* Glover. All the tested biorationals reduced the sucking pest populations significantly over control. Two sprays of spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l, dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l and azadirachtin 10,000 ppm @ 1.0 ml/l were effective.

Keywords: Biorationals, okra, sucking pests

INTRODUCTION

In India, okra, *Abelmoschus esculentus* L. Moench (Malvaceae) is a commonly grown green vegetable cultivated throughout the year and it is ravaged by as many as 44 insect pests. Among the various insect pests, sucking pests like leafhopper, *Amrasca biguttula biguttula* (Ishida), whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) and aphid, *Aphis gossypii* (Glover) pose a major threat, affecting the okra production. The yield loss due to leafhopper desapping in okra amounts to 54 to 66 per cent (Satpathy *et al.*, 2004). The whitefly is most notorious among top hundred insect pests having a pandemic distribution and damaging many important crops including vegetables, tubers, fiber crops and ornamentals (Abdel-Baky and Al-Deghairi, 2008). Apart from direct damage by sucking plant sap, it is also known as the vector for deadly yellow vein mosaic virus. Due to its rapid movement from one plant to another, high reproductive potential and its living habitat, management of the pest is very difficult (Fouly *et al.*, 2011). Farmers rely on conventional insecticides such as organophosphates, carbamates and synthetic pyrethroids to manage these sucking pests. The repeated use of systemic insecticides has resulted in the development of resistance in the insect pest and disturbance to the agro-ecosystem by affecting the non-targets. Hence, the present study was carried out to evaluate the efficacy of biorationals to find out a viable option for sustainable management of sucking insects.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The seeds of okra cv. Arka Anamika were sown during kharif 2015 in the experimental farm, Division of Entomology, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Bengaluru. After two weeks of sowing, the seedlings were thinned out and a spacing of 60 cm X 30 cm was maintained and good crop raised with standard agronomic practices. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design and consisted of six biorationals, one standard check and a control. All the treatments were replicated thrice. Two sprays at fortnightly interval were given and three plants were randomly selected and tagged in each plot for observing the insect population. The insect population counts were recorded from three leaves one at the top, middle and bottom from each plant. The population of leafhopper, whitefly and aphid counts were recorded one day prior to spraying and three, seven and fifteen days after spraying (DAS). The population data were subjected to suitable statistical analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Efficacy against leafhopper

Mean data on efficacy of various treatments recorded at different days after application revealed that all the treatments were significantly effective over the control in reducing the leafhopper population. The

Table 1. Evaluation of biorationals against *A. biguttula biguttula* on okra

Treatment	Mean no. of leafhoppers/three leaves (n=15 plants)										
	I Spray					II Spray					Pooled
	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	Mean
Azadirachtin (10,000 ppm) @ 1ml/l	6.86 (2.71)	3.50 (2.00)	3.34 (1.96)	3.48 (2.00)	3.44	7.16 (2.76)	2.96 (1.86)	2.63 (1.77)	2.70 (1.79)	2.76	3.10
<i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i> @ 2 g/l	7.02 (2.74)	3.81 (2.08)	3.54 (2.01)	3.33 (1.96)	3.56	7.22 (2.78)	3.00 (1.87)	2.79 (1.80)	2.85 (1.83)	2.88	3.22
Neem soap @ 10 g/l	6.95 (2.72)	3.95 (2.11)	3.79 (2.07)	3.86 (2.09)	3.86	7.33 (2.80)	3.67 (2.04)	3.42 (1.98)	3.58 (2.02)	3.55	3.71
Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l	6.93 (2.73)	4.24 (2.18)	4.16 (2.16)	4.29 (2.19)	4.23	7.22 (2.77)	3.90 (2.10)	3.75 (2.06)	3.85 (2.09)	3.63	3.93
Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l	7.04 (2.75)	3.75 (2.06)	3.67 (2.04)	3.93 (2.10)	3.78	7.35 (2.80)	3.35 (1.96)	3.20 (1.92)	3.48 (1.99)	3.34	3.56
Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l	6.99 (2.74)	2.27 (1.66)	1.34 (1.35)	0.35 (0.92)	1.32	7.18 (2.77)	2.57 (1.75)	1.87 (1.54)	1.07 (1.23)	1.83	1.58
Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l	7.01 (2.74)	3.35 (1.96)	2.49 (1.72)	2.53 (1.74)	2.79	7.26 (2.78)	2.75 (1.80)	2.49 (1.73)	2.24 (1.66)	2.49	2.64
Untreated control	7.12 (2.76)	7.25 (2.78)	7.43 (2.82)	7.66 (2.85)	7.44	7.28 (2.79)	7.33 (2.80)	7.43 (2.82)	7.69 (2.86)	7.48	7.46
CD at 5%	NS	0.37	0.62	0.49	-	NS	0.44	0.79	0.51	-	-
SEm \pm	-	0.12	0.20	0.16	-	-	0.14	0.26	0.17	-	-

DBS - Day before spraying, DAS - Days after spraying

Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{X + 0.5}$ transformed values**Table 2. Evaluation of biorationals against *B. tabaci* on okra**

Treatment	Mean no. of whiteflies/three leaves (n=15 plants)										
	I Spray					II Spray					Pooled
	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	Mean
Azadirachtin (10,000 ppm) @ 1ml/l	7.82 (2.88)	3.92 (2.10)	3.71 (2.05)	3.68 (2.04)	3.77	6.23 (2.59)	3.10 (1.90)	2.99 (1.87)	3.12 (1.90)	3.07	3.42
<i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i> @ 2 g/l	8.04 (2.92)	4.28 (2.18)	3.97 (2.11)	4.08 (2.14)	4.11	6.09 (2.56)	3.44 (1.98)	3.30 (1.95)	3.27 (1.94)	3.33	3.72
Neem soap @10 g/l	7.95 (2.90)	4.42 (2.22)	4.21 (2.17)	4.35 (2.20)	4.32	6.48 (2.64)	3.87 (2.09)	3.81 (2.08)	3.98 (2.12)	3.88	4.10
Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l	7.78 (2.88)	4.72 (2.28)	4.62 (2.26)	4.77 (2.30)	4.70	6.42 (2.63)	3.78 (2.07)	3.82 (2.08)	4.02 (2.13)	3.87	4.29
Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l	8.13 (2.94)	4.06 (2.13)	3.97 (2.11)	4.11 (2.15)	4.04	6.30 (2.60)	3.29 (1.95)	3.16 (1.91)	3.20 (1.92)	3.21	3.63
Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l	8.15 (2.94)	3.42 (1.98)	2.13 (1.60)	0.87 (1.17)	2.14	6.19 (2.59)	2.54 (1.74)	0.92 (1.19)	0.50 (1.00)	1.32	1.73
Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l	8.07 (2.93)	3.78 (2.07)	3.18 (1.91)	3.02 (1.88)	3.32	6.26 (2.60)	2.71 (1.79)	2.51 (1.74)	2.47 (1.72)	2.56	2.94
Untreated control	8.15 (2.94)	8.28 (2.96)	8.41 (2.98)	8.66 (3.02)	8.45	6.57 (2.65)	6.64 (2.67)	6.71 (2.69)	6.82 (2.71)	6.72	7.59
CD at 5%	NS	0.53	0.79	0.94	-	NS	0.37	0.34	0.28	-	-
SEm \pm	-	0.17	0.26	0.31	-	-	0.12	0.11	0.09	-	-

DBS - Day before spraying, DAS - Days after spraying

Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{X + 0.5}$ transformed values

Table 3. Evaluation of biorationals against *A. gossypii* on okra

Treatment	Mean no. of aphids/three leaves (n=15 plants)										
	I Spray					II Spray					Pooled
	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	DBS	3 DAS	7 DAS	15 DAS	Mean	Mean
Azadirachtin (10,000 ppm) @ 1ml/l	23.14 (4.86)	16.52 (4.12)	10.55 (3.32)	9.21 (3.11)	12.09	20.70 (4.60)	13.35 (3.72)	9.80 (3.21)	9.94 (3.23)	11.03	11.56
<i>Lecanicillium lecanii</i> @ 2 g/l	22.44 (4.79)	18.47 (4.36)	14.55 (3.88)	15.45 (3.99)	16.15	20.24 (4.55)	14.39 (3.86)	13.25 (3.71)	13.60 (3.75)	13.74	14.95
Neem soap @ 10 g/l	22.82 (4.83)	19.51 (4.47)	13.01 (3.67)	14.56 (3.88)	15.69	22.04 (4.75)	15.56 (4.01)	14.12 (3.82)	14.95 (3.93)	14.87	15.28
Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml/l	23.23 (4.87)	19.67 (4.49)	15.23 (3.96)	15.86 (4.04)	16.92	21.80 (4.72)	17.11 (4.20)	15.22 (3.96)	16.18 (4.08)	16.17	16.55
Organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l	23.01	18.20 (4.85)	11.61 (4.32)	12.25 (3.48)	14.02 (3.57)	21.29	13.57 (4.67)	11.34 (3.75)	11.98 (3.44)	12.29 (3.53)	13.16
Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l	24.06 (4.96)	12.13 (3.55)	7.29 (2.79)	4.17 (2.16)	7.86	22.71 (4.81)	10.88 (3.37)	4.78 (2.29)	3.68 (2.04)	6.44	7.15
Dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6 ml/l	22.70 (4.81)	15.23 (3.97)	9.75 (3.20)	7.27 (2.78)	10.75	21.34 (4.67)	13.08 (3.69)	7.95 (2.90)	8.15 (2.94)	9.72	10.24
Untreated control	22.81 (4.83)	23.14 (4.86)	24.27 (4.98)	25.44 (5.09)	24.28	23.00 (4.84)	23.86 (4.94)	24.38 (4.99)	25.50 (5.10)	24.58	24.43
CD at 5%	NS	1.50	1.20	1.96	-	NS	1.34	1.41	1.19	-	-
SEm±		-	0.49	0.39	0.64	-	-	0.44	0.46	0.39	-

DBS - Day before spraying, DAS - Days after spraying

Figures in parentheses are $\sqrt{X} + 0.5$ transformed values

population of leafhopper per three leaves in different treated treatments ranged from 1.58 to 3.93 against 7.46 in control. Two sprays of spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l were found to be highly effective. Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml was found to be least effective against leafhopper followed by neem soap @10.0 g/l and organic salt 30 WS @ 5 ml/l. The present findings are in comparison with those of Aparna and Dethe (2012) who reported that the spinosad was effective in controlling the leafhoppers.

Efficacy against whitefly

The mean pooled data of two sprays recorded significant differences over control; it ranged from 1.73 to 4.29 whiteflies/three leaves from the treatments of spinosad @ 0.2 ml/l and organic salt @ 4 ml/l. Two sprays of spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l was found to be highly effective, which is in agreement with the reports of Kumar and Poehling (2007), who reported that spinosad and Neem Azal-T/S (azadirachtin) were more effective against whiteflies.

Efficacy against aphids

The population of aphids per three leaves in different treated treatments ranged from 7.15 to 16.55 as against 24.43 in control. Spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l was found to be highly effective. Organic salt 30 WS @ 4 ml was found to be least effective against aphids. Similarly, Singh and Singh (2009) reported that spinosad and dimethoate recorded significantly less number of aphids. On rape and Indian mustard spinosad 45 SC @ 0.2 ml/l was found to be most effective for the management of different sucking pests followed by dimethoate 30 EC @ 1.6ml/l.

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